

Two-phase flow model for porous media applied to a plate fin heat exchanger

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Abstract

Porous media have been widely used in industrial applications such as car radiator, electronic cooling, geothermal system, and others. Channels with high fins density can be considered as a porous media represented by a porous matrix. It is defined by its specific transport properties. That means that it is not resolved explicitly but represented by a volumetric porous zone where a volume-averaged pressure gradient drag term is applied to the Navier–Stokes momentum equation. Porous media in heat exchanger industry is mostly used to gain on computational power, a compromise between classic local CFD, which is the most precise but costly and empirical correlation, which are simple but imprecise and limited by geometries. This paper will be testing a porous two-phase code in industrial HX condition and comparing it to recommended empirical correlations.

Keywords: CFD, Porous media, Heat exchanger, Heat transfer, Mass transfer, Multiphase flow

1. Nomenclature

α : Volume fraction

t : Time

ϵ : Porosity

Y : Mass fraction

ρ : Density

e : Internal energy

E : Total energy

u : velocity

μ : Dynamic viscosity

P : Pressure

k_{eff} : Effective conductivity

\dot{m} : Mass transfer rate

μ_p : Pressure equilibrium coefficient

λ_v : Velocity equilibrium coefficient

H_T : Thermal equilibrium coefficient

C_p : Specific heat

λ : Conductivity

γ : Heat capacity ratio

k : Permeability

k_1 : Inertial permeability

L_{LV} : Latent heat

T_{sat} : Saturation temperature

P_{sat} : Saturation pressure

β : Inertial resistance coefficient

$S p_{porous}$: Specific surface of porous only

$S p_{base}$: Specific surface of base only

Nu : Nusselt number

Re : Reynolds number

j : Colburn factor

f : Fanning friction factor

D_h : Hydraulic diameter
 G : Mass flow rate
 V : Volume of medium
 V_f : Volume of fluid in medium
 g : Chemical potential
 A_I : Interfacial specific area

2. Introduction

A heat exchanger is a widely used device that exchanges heat between two fluids or gas. The design of heat exchangers can be a complicated problem if it takes into account not only heat-transfer analysis alone, but the cost of fabrication and installation among other things. Although cost is an important consideration, size and footprint are usually the dominant factors in choosing a design.

Often the heat exchanger is designed using empirical correlations. Yet, one of the most dynamically improving research field is the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), which is a good alternative of the expensive and time demanding experimental test measurements. Meanwhile the simulation methods often are not just a more cost efficient solution than experimental measurements, but even provide more details and information about a given problem. Analytical approaches permit to calculate average values, but not the local values. Meanwhile, the CFD calculation permits to calculate the local values, but this method can be very expensive for complex products.

Likewise, there are commercial software to calculate not only CFD, but also the stress analysis and optimization calculation.

Although numerous semi-empirical correlations are available in the literature for estimating the convection coefficient of tube bundles with solid fins, the values predicted by such correlations rarely agree with one another, and in some cases can differ by as much as 30%. A compromise between empirical correlations and full CFD modeling in the case of heat exchangers, is the porous media approach, where for example the finned tube bundles in a heat exchanger are represented by a porous matrix, which is defined by its porosity, permeability, and the form drag coefficient. The porosity is equal to the tube bundle volumetric void fraction and the permeability is calculated by using correlations.

This paper focuses on the verification of a two-phase flow model for porous media implemented in a numerical code in its application to the design of a plate fin heat exchanger, as it is compared to the GRETH's

pre-design software (Echtherm) for industrial heat exchanger which features multiple empirical correlations and indicate the best fitting one for each case.

3. State of the art

Multiple developments were made surrounding the numerical modelization of heat exchangers with porous media. A first work by [1] to develop a scientific procedure for optimization of heat exchanger geometry. As a part of this program an integral numerical code for modeling of heat exchangers was constructed. The numerical code is based on Volume Averaging Technique (VAT) for a porous media flow, which was presented by Whitaker [2]. Treating the Heat exchanger core as porous medium is a way to make code fast and suitable for the surface optimization calculations. The heat exchanger internal structure, in form of isothermal tubes and is treated as a homogenous porous media. The local values of drag and heat transfer coefficients that were needed to close the transport equations were taken from [3]. The resulting partial differential equations were discretized using the conservation properties of the finite volume method (FVM). The resulting system of semilinear equations was then solved with a preconditioned conjugate gradient method. In this paper he calculated values of drag and heat transfer coefficients show excellent agreement with published data.

A multi-scale model for two-phase simulation of multi-stream plate-fin heat exchangers was developed in [4]. Important features in a multi-stream HX simulation, such as phase change phenomena, multi-component mixtures, multiple streams, transversal, lateral and longitudinal conduction, non-uniformity of inlet flow, variable fluid properties, and heat leakage are simultaneously considered in this model.

The following assumption are considered: Steady-state operation, the temperature variation along the thickness of plates is negligible, the mass flow distributions are known and do not vary in the flow direction and the conduction heat transfer through the fluid is neglected in comparison with the heat conduction within the solid. Porous approach was not used in this study and each domain and sub-domain of the exchanger was discretized in computational elements governing equations are derived separately, and thermal interactions are addressed by their com-

mon boundary conditions.

Another case was simulated by Pozhilov and al. [5], for the heat and mass transfer in a 3D model of a loop heat pipe evaporator. This simulation included the model of Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations describing the flow in the liquid and vapor regions, Darcy’s law for filtration modeling in the wicks (porous structure) and the energy equation with an accurate coupling of connected sub-domains that includes the effects of evaporation on interfaces between the porous and vapor regions.

In [5] and [1] local thermal equilibrium is assumed, meaning that at the interface, fluid and porous structure are at the same temperature. Unless one is working with higher velocity flows (3m/s for air) [6] this assumption usually gives unrealistic prediction and thermal-non equilibrium is mostly used when investigating phase change flows.

In [7], a CFD model using a commercial software is developed for better understanding the transport phenomena, especially the phase change, in a plate-fin heat exchanger used for gas refining. The flow channels, ducts and passes of the cold box, are considered in the computational geometry. The porous media technique is introduced in the computational domain due to the excessive increase in the number of computational grids when the fins accounted for in the numerical domain. A flash calculations (FC) technique is coupled with CFD in evaluation of chemical species in the cold box by a user defined function. This study examines the importance of local thermal equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow without mass transfer, local thermal equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow with mass transfer (LTE), and local thermal non equilibrium between the porous medium and fluid flow with mass transfer (LTNE).

4. Model description

4.1. Multi-phase model

The implemented model is from Baer & Nunziato (1986) and has 7 equations, for phase-separated compressible flows and each phase obeys its own thermodynamics.

$$\frac{\delta\alpha_1}{\delta t} + \vec{u}_1 \cdot \vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho)_1}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha\rho\vec{u})_1 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho)_2}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha\rho\vec{u})_2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho\vec{u})_1}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho\vec{u}\vec{u} + P\vec{I}))_1 = P_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho\vec{u})_2}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho\vec{u}\vec{u} + P\vec{I}))_2 = P_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho E)_1}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho E + P))_1 = P_1\vec{u}_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho E)_2}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho E + P))_2 = P_1\vec{u}_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 \quad (7)$$

Each phase has its own state equation to close its system, the ideal gas law for the vapor phase and Tate-Tamman law for the liquid phase. Several simplifying hypothesis are applied to this model. Pressure equilibrium between phases is considered (μ_p tends towards infinite) as well as thermal equilibrium (H_T tends towards infinite) in an homogeneous mixture. No velocity slip between phases is considered (λ_v tends towards infinite) and chemical potential are at non-equilibrium ($\dot{m} = \rho v(g_1 - g_2)$ translate the mass transfer, with v the the equilibrium velocity of chemical potential) which implies a finite rate mass transfer. The final system yields:

$$\frac{\delta\alpha_1}{\delta t} + \vec{u}_1 \cdot \vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 = \mu_p(P_1 - P_2) - \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_1} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho)_1}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha\rho\vec{u})_1 = -\dot{m} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho\vec{u})_2}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho\vec{u}\vec{u} + P\vec{I}))_2 \\ &= P_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 + \lambda_v(\vec{u}_2 - \vec{u}_1) - \dot{m}\vec{u}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\delta(\alpha\rho E)_2}{\delta t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha(\rho E + P))_2 \\ &= P_1\vec{u}_1\vec{\nabla}\alpha_1 - \mu_p P_1(P_1 - P_2) \\ &+ \lambda_v\vec{u}_1(\vec{u}_2 - \vec{u}_1) + H_T(T_2 - T_1) - \dot{m}H_1 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

It is to this final model that source terms like the flow law defining the porous media will be applied.

4.2. Porous model

The first characteristic of a porous medium is its porosity: this is the ratio between the volume not containing solids and the total volume of the medium V :

$$\epsilon = \frac{V_f}{V} \quad (12)$$

In the porous domain, the pressure losses are defined by the Darcy-Forchheimer law, for the ΔP in the x-direction it yields:

$$\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} = -\frac{\mu}{k}u - \frac{\rho}{k_1}u^2 \quad (13)$$

With k the permeability and k_1 the inertial permeability, the permeability of a porous material is its capacity to let a fluid pass through it. A good permeability therefore implies a good porosity, but the opposite is not necessarily true, it has been shown to be intrinsic to the solid matrix of the porous medium and therefore only a function of its topology and its associated geometric properties.

The heat transfer in the porous media is treated with a local thermal non-equilibrium with the following thermal aspects:

Conduction in the solid matrix:

$$(1 - \epsilon)(\rho C p)_s \frac{\delta T_s}{\delta t} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (k_s^{eff} \nabla T_s) \quad (14)$$

Conduction in the fluid volume:

$$\epsilon(\rho C p)_f \frac{\delta T_f}{\delta t} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (k_f^{eff} \nabla T_f) \quad (15)$$

Heat transfer between fluid and solid:

$$\pm h_{sf} \alpha_{sf} (T_s - T_f) \quad (16)$$

4.3. Phase change model

Local phase change rate is finite as chemical potential relaxation is not considered. The thermodynamic state at the liquid-vapor interface is assumed to be at saturation (saturation pressure and temperature at the interface), with:

$$\frac{\delta \rho Y_1}{\delta t} = -\dot{m} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{m} = \frac{(h_{T2} + h_{T1})(T - T_{sat})}{L_{VL}} \quad (18)$$

Where $L_{VL} = f(T_{sat})$ and $T_{sat} = f(P)$ and $h_{Tk} = H_{Tk} A_I$

5. Test case description

Validation through correlations of each physics in the code:

- Single phase heat transfer (analytic solution for the base), with and without a porous domain.
- Two-phase (Evaporation and condensation) heat transfer, with and without a porous domain.

5.1. Geometry

The channel chosen for the testing is a representative one of Liebherr's evaporator as the code aim is to simulate this type of heat exchanger. The test channel have the following dimensions:

Table 1: Test channel geometry

length	height	width
mm	mm	mm
296.5	2.4136	49.5

The channel 2D model in the code is meshed with a Cartesian mesh of 20 cells in the y-direction (height) and 200 cells in the x-direction (length).

Figure 1: Meshed test channel

5.2. Fluid and solid properties

The working fluid is water at 10^5 Pa with the following properties for both phases:

Table 2: Water properties gas and liquid

	λ	μ	Cp	γ
	(W/mK)	Pa.s	(J/kg.K)	-
Liquid	0.6	10^{-3}	4180	1.33
Vapor	0.03	10^{-5}	2000	1.3

The porous properties of the finned channel, with $S p_{porous}$ the specific porous surface alone, and $S p_{base}$ the specific base surface alone:

Table 3: Porous properties

ϵ	β	k	$S p_{porous}$	$S p_{base}$
-	(m^{-1})	(m^2)	(m^2/m^3)	(m^2/m^3)
0.86	78	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.64	1.74

5.3. Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions applied at the inlet and outlet are respectively a uniform velocity condition ($v=0.014$ m/s) and a pressure condition ($P=10^{-5}$). In the case without mass transfer the inlet temperature in

293K and in the case including phase-change the inlet temperature is 392K. The inlet mass fraction of liquid is set to 1 for every case. A uniform heat flux of $1000W/m^2$ is applied at the north and south boundary of the 2D model.

6. Empirical correlations

6.1. Single phase heat transfer correlation

The Nusselt of a single phase flow between two plates admit an exact solution in the case of a set temperature or heat flux.

Temperature:

$$Nu = 7.54 \quad (19)$$

Heat Flux:

$$Nu = 8.24 \quad (20)$$

6.2. Single phase porous pressure drop correlations

Wieting and Joshi correlations are recommended for pressure loss on channels of this type with offsets fins by the Echtherm software.

With fins geometrical characteristics:

- h : fin height
- s : fins spacing
- δ : fin width

Hydraulic diameter for offset fins is defined by:

$$Dh = 2 \frac{sh}{s+h} \quad (21)$$

Wieting correlation [8] is based on 22 tested geometries. For the pressure losses, with j the colburn factor and f the fanning friction factor, is the following:

$$f = 1.136 \left(\frac{L}{Dh} \right)^{-0.781} \left(\frac{\delta}{h} \right)^{0.534} Re^{-0.198} \quad (22)$$

For roughly the same configuration, Joshi and Webb, after carrying out a momentum and energy balance on an elementary model, suggest the following correlations based on 21 tested geometries:

$$f = 1.12 \left(\frac{L}{Dh} \right)^{-0.65} \left(\frac{\delta}{Dh} \right)^{0.17} Re^{-0.36} \quad (23)$$

6.3. Two phase heat transfer correlation

To determine the heat transfer coefficient (HTC) in phase changing cases the Shah correlation [9] for two-phase flows is used, with h_{tp} being the two-phase heat transfer coefficient and h_l the liquid single phase one:

$$\phi = h_{tp}/h_l \quad (24)$$

The N parameter is defined as follow: For vertical tubes at all values of Fr and for horizontal tubes with $Fr_l \geq 0.04$.

$$N = Co \quad (25)$$

For horizontal tube with $Fr_l \leq 0.04$,

$$N = 0.38 Fr_l^{-0.3} Co \quad (26)$$

with,

$$Co = \left(\frac{1}{x} - 1 \right)^{0.8} \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_l} \right)^{0.5} \quad (27)$$

For $N \geq 1.0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{nb} &= 230 Bo^{0.5} & , Bo > 0.3 * 10^{-4} \\ \phi_{nb} &= 1 + 46 Bo^{0.5} & , Bo < 0.3 * 10^{-4} \\ \phi_{cb} &= \frac{1.8}{N^{0.8}} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

ϕ is the larger of ϕ_{nb} and ϕ_{cb} .

For $0.1 \leq N \leq 1.0$:

$$\phi_{bs} = F Bo^{0.5} exp^{2.47N^{-0.1}} \quad (29)$$

ϕ_{cb} is calculated using the same equation as before, ϕ is again the larger of ϕ_{bs} and ϕ_{cb} .

For $N \leq 0.1$:

$$\phi_{bs} = F Bo^{0.5} exp^{2.47N^{-0.15}} \quad (30)$$

ϕ is again the larger of ϕ_{bs} and ϕ_{cb} . The F constant is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Bo \geq 11 * 10^{-4} & , F = 14.7 \\ Bo \leq 11 * 10^{-4} & , F = 15.42 \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

6.4. Two phase porous pressure drop correlation

As no slip velocity between phases is considered, the homogeneous flow model is assumed in the gas and liquid two-phase mixture. The properties of the two-phase mixture are calculated with the gas quality and the properties of liquid and gas fluids.

The pressure loss is expressed as a function of a multiplication factor (Lockhart and Martinelli parameter [10]) and the frictional pressure loss calculated as if the liquid or gas were flowing alone in the pipe. For a two-component system, we write:

$$-\frac{dP}{dz} = \Phi_G^2 \left(\frac{dP}{dz} \right)_G = \Phi_L^2 \left(\frac{dP}{dz} \right)_L \quad (32)$$

The single phase pressure drop term (L for liquid and G for gas) is determined from the classical equations

(Wieting & Joshi [8]). The multiplication factor is determined from various correlations based on the separate fluid model.

$$X^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{dP}{dz}\right)_L}{\left(\frac{dP}{dz}\right)_G} \quad (33)$$

Christholm [11] gives a simple analytical representation:

$$\Phi_l^2 = 1 + \frac{C}{X} + \frac{1}{X^2} \quad (34)$$

$$\Phi_G^2 = 1 + CX + X^2 \quad (35)$$

where the constant C depends on the flow regime of the liquid and the gas circulating alone in the tube.

Liquide	Gaz	C
Turbulent	Turbulent	20
Laminaire	Turbulent	12
Turbulent	Laminaire	10
Laminaire	Laminaire	5

Figure 2: C constant function of flow regime

Initially investigated for two-component systems, the method is also applicable to systems with phase change.

7. Results

The simulation results are presented bellow and compared to the introduced correlation in 6. Observation will be discussed in 8

7.1. Single-phase heat transfer and pressure loss

The heat transfer coefficient without porous domain is calculated and compared to the exact solution in the case of a set heat flux applied uniformly to a surface.

Figure 3: HTC without porous function of fluid temperature with a Nusselt solution for wall heat flux (orange)

Figure 4: Pressure profile along the channel

In figure 4 the pressure evolution along the channel is plotted and the pressure drop is compared in Table 4 Pressure drop is calculated from the middle of the domain to the end on $x/2$ to only consider the linear part of the pressure losses, it is the double to account for the whole channel.

Table 4: Pressure drop comparison to correlation

	Code	Wieting	Joshi
ΔP	$0.03 \cdot 10^5$	$0.16 \cdot 10^5$	$0.21 \cdot 10^5$
ERROR	0%	12.3%	17.1%

Figure 5: Pressure profile in the channel

Figure 6: Temperature profile in the porous matrix

Figures 5 and 6 shows an example of the obtained value fields with the code for the pressure field and the temperature field in the solid porous matrix.

7.2. Two-phase heat transfer and pressure loss

Figure 7 shows the pressure profile in the test channel for the two-phase (boiling) flow case. Pressure drop is calculated on the linear part of the profile, as in the preceding case. It is of $0.4 \cdot 10^5$ Pa. When the empirical correlation yields $0.56 \cdot 10^5$ Pa.

Figure 7: Pressure profile along the channel

Figures 8, 9 and 10 shows the heat transfer function of the mass fraction of liquid, the simulation was carried out on the non porous case ($\epsilon=1$), on the HX channel ($\epsilon=0.86$) and on an additional case with a porosity of 0.9.

On each plot the empirical correlation result is plotted for the liquid mass fraction of 0.95, 0.9 and 0.85. Figure 11 shows the temperature profil in the solid matrix in boiling flow conditions.

Figure 8: HTC function of mass fraction of liquid for $\epsilon=0.86$ (blue) and correlation solution for $X = 0.95$ (orange)

Figure 9: HTC function of mass fraction of liquid for $\epsilon=0.9$ (blue) and correlation solution for $X = 0.9$ (orange)

Figure 10: HTC function of mass fraction of liquid for $\epsilon=1$ (blue) and correlation solution for $X = 0.85$ (orange)

Figure 11: Temperature profile in the solid for $\epsilon=0.86$

8. Discussions

On the heat transfer coefficient one can see that it tends to decrease with the mass fraction of liquid. Which is in agreement with what is found in literature, before 90% of vapor rate, gas mixture intensifies the transfer. Overall the evolution of the liquid mass fraction in low over the length of this sole channel to conclude on the evolution of the coefficient as a function of the vapour rate, but the order of magnitude at the same fraction is in agreement with the literature. On the pressure drops we observe almost the same gap with the correlation on the results, if the pressure correlations show less important deviation than that of exchange coefficient it remains very dependent on the geometry what induces systematically errors in the different configurations. The entry effects mean that the pressure drop cannot be evaluated directly between the inlet and the outlet, but by considering the second half of the channel in twice its size to be able to compare the linear pressure drop with the correlation, it is observed that it tends to be underestimated.

9. Conclusion

Error from correlatioms are within the range of acceptable for two-phase flows, for example in [12] multiple boiling flows correlations were reviewed and the MEA ranged from 59.4% to 28.1%. For single-phase flow the heat transfer coefficient is of the same order of magnitude as the one given by the Nusselt exact solution. This code if at this point only at pre design accuracy and will need an upgrade to 3D and improvement in boundary conditions options to become a tool for the design of heat exchangers.

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